

4th International Conference on Automation and Engineering (AUEN 2025)

January 23 ~ 24, 2025, Virtual Conference

<https://auen2025.org/index>

Scope & Topics

4th International Conference on Automation and Engineering (AUEN 2025) will provide an excellent international forum for sharing knowledge and results in theory, methodology and new advances and research results in the fields of Automation and Engineering. The conference will bring together researchers and practitioners from both academia as well as industry to meet and share cutting-edge development in the field. The Conference welcomes significant contributions in all major fields of the Automation in theoretical and practical aspects. Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following

- Automated usability and user experience testing
- Automation and control systems
- Control Theory
- Diagnostics and Reliability of Automatic Control Systems
- Flexible Manufacturing Systems
- Formal methods and theories for testing and test automation
- Industrial Automation Systems
- Process control, manufacturing process and automation
- Industrial Robotics and Mechatronic Systems
- Machine Learning, Big Data, Internet of Things
- Modeling and Simulation
- Natural Language Processing (NLP) Based Test Automation
- Network Automation
- NLP in Robotic Process Automation
- Robotics, Automation and Artificial Intelligence
- Computer Vision & Automation
- Robotics, Automation and Signal Processing
- Security Automation
- Software Test Automation
- Test automation of large, complex system
- Theoretical foundations of test automation

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers through the conference [Submission System](#) by **November 23, 2024**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this conference. The proceedings of the conference will be published by [International Journal on Cybernetics & Informatics \(IJCI\)](#) (Confirmed).

Selected papers from **AUEN 2025**, after further revisions, will be published in the special issues of the following journals

- [International journal of Software Engineering & Applications \(IJSEA\)](#)
- [Machine Learning and Applications: An International Journal \(MLAIJ\)](#)
- [International Journal of Information Technology, Control and Automation \(IJITCA\)](#)

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : November 23, 2024**
- Authors Notification : December 14, 2024
- Registration & Camera-Ready Paper Due : December 21, 2024

Contact Us

Here's where you can reach us: auen@auen2025.org (or) auenconf@yahoo.com

For other details: <https://auen2025.org/index>

Paper Submission Link: <https://auen2025.org/submission/index.php>